

Polarographic Study of the Complexes formed by Zinc, Manganese, Nickel and Cobalt with 1:2 Diaminocyclohexanetetra-acetic Acid

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The reduction, composition, stability constants and analytical uses of the complexes formed by 1:2 Diaminocyclohexanetetra-acetic acid with Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} have been studied at the dropping mercury electrode. The results have been summarised as below:—

- (1) All the complexes formed are non-reducible.
- (2) From amperometric study it is clear that the complexes are formed in 1:1 ratio. The complexes are stable in weakly acidic and alkaline solution. Thus Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} can be estimated amperometrically by titrating against standard EDTA solution.
- (3) The log K_{stz} values of Zn^{2+} at $\mu=0.1$ comes to be 18.5 and at $\mu=1.0$ is 18.05 whereas, that for Co^{2+} was found to be 18.57 at $\mu=0.1$ and 18.27 at $\mu=1.0$ respectively. This shows that stability constants decrease with the increase of ionic strength. The error in log K_{stz} values is about $\pm 0.2\%$. The method could not be applied for Mn^{2+} and Ni^{2+} . Stability constants at 20°C for Zn^{2+} and Co^{2+} have been reported by Schwarzenbach¹, which shows that the log K_{stz} have lower values at 25° than at 20°, indicating that stability constant decreases with the increase of temperature.

1 : 2 Diaminocyclohexanetetra-acetic acid (CDTA or H_4Z) forms stable complexes with many metallic ions. It is very similar to ethylenediaminetetra-acetic acid (EDTA) in its complexing action. Schwarzenbach and coworkers have determined the stability constants of the CDTA complexes with many metal ions and it has been reported that the stability constants of the chelates formed by this compound are higher in comparison to the corresponding EDTA complexes¹. The complexes formed by lead², cadmium³, gallium and indium⁴ and some rare-earth metal ions⁵ with CDTA have been studied by the authors. The present paper reports the reduction, composition, stability constants and analytical uses of the complexes formed by zinc, manganese, nickel and cobalt with 1 : 2 Diaminocyclohexanetetra-acetic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents :—The CDTA as supplied by L. Light & Co. was used and the solution of its disodium salt was prepared and the purity of the sample was checked by titrating it against standard solution of zinc using Eriochrome Black T. as indicator⁶. The solutions

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4. Jain D. S. and Gaur J. N., *J. Less-Common Metals* (communicated).
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6. Biedermann, W. and Schwarzenbach, G., *Chimia*, 1948, 2, 56.

of the metals were prepared from their nitrates. All the chemicals used were of reagent grade purity. Sodium perchlorate was used as a supporting electrolyte and Triton X₁₀₀ as supplied by Rohm Hass & Co. was used as a maximum suppressor. During amperometric titrations, buffers of different pH were used⁷. Purified nitrogen as supplied by Indian Oxygen & Co. was used for deaeration.

Apparatus :—All the polarograms were recorded with L.P. 55 Heyrovsky system polarograph and the amperometric titrations were carried out on a manual set up⁷. The dropping mercury electrode had the following characteristics: $m=2.12$ mg/sec. and $t = 3.6$ sec. (at -1.0 V vs S.C.E. in 0.1 M potassium nitrate solution). All the measurements were done at $25 \pm 0.01^\circ$ which was controlled by a Haske type ultra thermostat. The pH of the solution was adjusted by the addition of sodium hydroxide or perchloric acid and was measured by a battery operated bench type Cambridge pH meter. During the actual measurement of the current in amperometric titrations, the supply of gas was cut off and the gas was passed for a minute after each addition of the titrant to insure complete reaction and deaeration. The diffusion current was corrected for small dilution effect. The other details of the titrations have been given elsewhere⁸.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

(a) **Reduction of the Complexes**.—Zinc-CDTA Complex :—Solutions containing 1mM Zn^{2+} , 2mM CDTA in 1M potassium chloride at different pH were prepared and polarographed. It was found that below pH 6, the hydrogen wave interferes and at and above pH 7, the supporting electrolyte decomposes before the reduction of the complex, which shows that complex is non-reducible.

Manganese-CDTA Complex :—Solutions containing 1mM Mn^{2+} , 2mM CDTA in 1M potassium chloride at different pH were prepared and polarographed. In acidic solutions, the measurements were not possible because the half-wave potential for the hydrogen discharge closely follows the reduction of Mn^{2+} . In alkaline solution, no reduction wave appears before the decomposition of the supporting electrolyte.

Nickel-CDTA Complex :—Solutions containing 1mM Ni^{2+} , 2mM CDTA in 0.1M sodium perchlorate at different pH were prepared and polarographed. No reduction wave appears before the decomposition of the base electrolyte.

Cobalt-CDTA Complex :—Solutions containing 1mM Co^{2+} , 2mM CDTA in 1M sodium sulphate were prepared at different pH. Similar results were obtained as in case of Ni^{2+} .

(b) **Composition of the Complexes** : Zinc-CDTA Complex :—Solutions containing same amount of Zn^{2+} at different pH were prepared. The buffer solutions used for pH control acted as supporting electrolytes. The titration curve is of L shape (Fig. 1).

Reverse titrations were also carried out (Fig. 2).

From the above results (direct as well as reverse titrations), it is clear that the ratio of Zn^{2+} : CDTA is less than unity below pH 6. Above this pH value, the ratio comes to be

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8. Jain D. S., *Ph. D. Thesis*, Rajasthan University, Jaipur, 1965.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

1:1. Above pH 10, direct titrations could not be carried out due to the hydrolysis of zinc salt. It shows that Zn^{2+} forms 1:1 complex with CDTA, which is stable in slightly acidic and alkaline solution. The formula of the complex is ZnZ^{2-} .

Manganese-CDTA Complex:—Solutions containing same amount of Mn^{2+} at different pH were prepared. It was found that in the presence of buffer solutions no reduction wave appeared, thus titrations could not be done under these conditions. But however, when potassium chloride was added, the reduction wave appeared. Thus potassium chloride was added as supporting electrolyte (0.1M). The results of the direct titration have been shown in Fig. 3.

Reverse titrations were also done (pH 7-10). The results have been presented in Fig. 4

FIG. 3

The above results show that the ratio of Mn^{2+} : CDTA is less than unity below pH 7. Above this pH, the ratio comes to be 1. This indicates that Mn^{2+} forms 1:1 complex with the anion of CDTA which is stable at and about pH 7. The formula of the complex comes to be MnZ^{2-} .

Nickel-CDTA Complex:—Solutions containing same amount of Ni^{2+} at different pH, controlled by buffer solutions, which acted as carrying electrolytes, were prepared. The results of the direct titrations have been shown in Fig. 5.

Reverse titrations were also carried out (pH 7-10). The results have been presented in Fig. 6.

It was found that the ratio of Ni^{2+} :CDTA comes to be less than unity below pH 4. At and above this pH, the ratio comes to be 1:1. The formula of the complex is NiZ^{2-} .

This shows that Ni^{2+} forms a complex with CDTA in 1 : 1 ratio, which is stable in slightly acidic and alkaline solution.

FIG. 4

FIG. 5

FIG. 6

Cobalt-EDTA Complex:—Solutions containing same amount of Co^{2+} at different pH (controlled by buffer solutions) were prepared and titrated. The results of direct titrations have been shown in Fig. 7.

Titration were also carried out by reverse method and the results have been presented in Fig. 8.

From the above results, it is clear that below pH 5, the ratio of $Co^{2+}/EDTA$ is less than unity. However, at and above this pH, the ratio comes to be one. Thus Co^{2+} forms a complex in 1 : 1 ratio with EDTA, which is quite stable at and above pH 5.0.

(c) *Stability constants*:—Since the complexes are non-reducible at the dropping mercury electrode, the classical method due to Lingane⁹ or DeFord and Hume's method¹⁰ cannot be applied. For this purpose a method devised by Schwarzenbach and coworkers which has been discussed in detail⁸ has been utilised. The $\log K_{MX}$ for Copper-EDTA complex at 25° has been found to be 21.134 ($\mu=0.1$)⁸. The results have been reported in Table I and II.

The error is about $\pm 2\%$ in the estimation of uncomplexed copper which will cause the uncertainty in the values of $\log K_{MX}$. The uncertainty in $\log K_{MX}$ values for Zn^{2+} and

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10. DeFord, D. D. and Hume, D. N., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 5321.

FIG. 7

Direct amperometric titrations of Co^{2+} with
CDTA : $[\text{Co}]$, pH 3.0; $[\Delta]$, pH 7.0.

FIG. 8

Reverse amperometric titrations of Co^{2+}
with CDTA : $[\text{Co}^{2+}]$, pH 7.0 [Δ], pH 10.0, $\circ$.

TABLE I

$\mu=0.1$		Temp. = $25 \pm .01^\circ$	
Metal ion	Cu ²⁺ (%)	log K _{MZ}	K _{MZ}
Zn ²⁺	4.16	18.506	3.21×10^{18}
Mn ²⁺	uncertain	—	—
Ni ²⁺	100	—	—
Co ²⁺	5.0	18.576	3.76×10^{18}

TABLE II

$\mu=1.0$		Temp. = $25 \pm 01.^\circ$	
Metal ion	Cu ²⁺ (%)	log K _{MZ}	K _{MZ}
Zn ²⁺	2.85	18.048	1.11×10^{18}
Mn ²⁺	uncertain	—	—
Ni ²⁺	100	—	—
Co ²⁺	3.57	18.27	1.86×10^{18}

Co²⁺ is of the order of ± 0.2 . The percentage of free copper in case of Mn²⁺ is too small to be estimated polarographically and in case of Ni²⁺, the whole of the copper is in free state, hence values of log K_{MZ} could not be determined in the above cases. The above results show that the complex of Mn²⁺ with respect of Cu²⁺ is much weaker and that of Ni²⁺ with respect of Cu²⁺ is much stronger.

(d) *Analytical uses* :—It is clear Zn²⁺, Mn²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Co²⁺ can be estimated amperometrically by titrating against standard CDTA solution since they form complexes in 1 : 1 ratio with the anion of CDTA. The formation of the complexes with bivalent metal ions can be explained as follows :

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